

ISic0351

Fragmentary epitaph, Faustina commemorates her mother

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2015.10.22 (right side only)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8742

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

undefined. [---]

1. [---]x an(nis) LXXVI m(ense) I
2. [---][---]avia C(ai) f(ilia) Faustina
3. [---]matri piae fecit

Apparatus

Text based upon CIL 10.7067

Translation (en)

[---] 76 years, 1 month. [---]avia Faustina, daughter of Gaius [---] made (this) for her dutiful mother

Commentary

Currently only the right half of this fragment has been located in the Siracusa stores

Digital identifiers:

TM 491560
EDR 141175
EDCS 21900389

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7067 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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